

Food insecurity in Malawi: Regional disparities, sociocultural determinants, and the role of mobile advisory services

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Agricultural technology

Technology adoptions

Malawi agriculture

Sustainable development goals

ABSTRACT

Food insecurity persists as a significant challenge globally, particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa, where structural, environmental, and socio-cultural factors exacerbate the crisis. In Malawi, regional disparities in food insecurity are pronounced, with the southern region heavily affected by environmental shocks, the central region plagued by soil degradation, and the northern region hindered by infrastructural gaps. This study bridges critical gaps in the literature by investigating regional and socio-cultural determinants of food insecurity while incorporating a novel farmer-driven technological intervention. Using a mixed-methods approach, the study combines thematic analyses of qualitative data with quantitative techniques, including Kruskal-Wallis tests, logistic regression, and conjoint analysis, to examine predictors of food security and adoption of mobile advisory services. Key findings reveal that education level has a significant influence on farmers' willingness to adopt mobile services, with cost and delivery mode emerging as pivotal factors in adoption preferences. The study highlights the importance of targeted, region-specific policies integrating technological interventions to enhance agricultural productivity, address systemic inequities, and promote resilience. These insights contribute to Sustainable Development Goal 2—Zero Hunger—by offering actionable strategies for addressing food insecurity in Malawi and similar contexts.

1. Introduction

Food insecurity remains a pressing global challenge despite decades of targeted interventions. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2022), food security exists “when all people, at all times, have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life.” This definition identifies four critical dimensions: food availability, economic and physical access, utilization, and stability. A comprehensive approach to food security requires that all four be met simultaneously and sustainably.

Globally, the food security landscape has deteriorated in recent years. In 2021, over 828 million people experienced hunger, and more

than 900 million faced severe food insecurity (Oli et al., 2025; FAO, 2022). By 2023, the number of people severely affected had surged to 345 million across 79 countries—double the figure in 2020 (FAO, 2022). Despite overall increases in global food production, inequitable distribution, climate change, conflict, and economic shocks have perpetuated hunger and malnutrition, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (WPF, 2025).

Sub-Saharan Africa bears a disproportionate share of this burden, accounting for 29 of the world's 40 most malnourished countries (Komushaago et al., 2023). Persistent structural challenges—such as land degradation, poor infrastructure, limited investment in agriculture, and political fragility—have weakened food systems despite growing regional food demand (Zuza et al., 2023; Beg et al., 2024; Aliyu et al.,

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2023). Furthermore, food insecurity has significant ripple effects on health and development, reducing life expectancy and increasing infant mortality (Beyene, 2023). Addressing these challenges aligns with both Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 2—Zero Hunger—and SDG 3.2, which focuses on reducing child mortality.

Malawi illustrates these broader concerns at the national scale. According to the *IPC Acute Food Insecurity Analysis (2024)*, approximately 4.2 million people—20 % of the population—were in IPC Phase 3 or above between May and September 2024. That number is projected to rise to 5.7 million between October 2024 and March 2025. Maize prices are now 160 % above the five-year average, straining household purchasing power (IPC, 2024). Compounding this, about 5.4 million people are experiencing chronic food insecurity due to recurring floods, prolonged dry spells, and entrenched poverty (WFP, 2022). Stunting rates among rural children remain high, especially in the Southern Region, where 39 % of children show signs of chronic undernutrition.

In addition to national trends, regional disparities in Malawi are increasingly pronounced. The Southern region faces environmental shocks and land scarcity, the Central region struggles with price instability and market inefficiencies, and the North contends with cultural constraints, such as patrilineal inheritance, that limit women's resource access (UN Women, UNDP, & UNEP, n.d.). Inflation has compounded these challenges—food prices rose by 36.0 % in February 2025, up from 33.7 % in December 2024 and 35.6 % in January 2025—thereby intensifying household food insecurity (FAO, 2025).

Malawi's input policies also reflect inefficiencies. Uniform fertilizer application, without regard to soil diversity, has led to nutrient imbalances and environmental degradation (Dhull et al., 2004; Titirmare et al., 2023). Urea-based fertilizers in acidic soils worsen acidification and reduce yield potential. Integrated Nutrient Management (INM), which combines organic and inorganic methods, provides a more sustainable solution alongside precision agriculture tools, such as GPS-guided variable-rate fertilization (Baradhan et al., 2022; Luo et al., 2024; Mangisoni et al., 2020).

The politicization of food aid has further undermined food security in Malawi. Programs like the Farm Input Subsidy Program (FISP), while designed to support smallholder farmers, are often manipulated for electoral gain rather than long-term agricultural reform (Banik & Chasukwa, 2019). Weak enforcement of land and food policies, along with limited accountability mechanisms, further impedes sustainable progress (Azomahou et al., 2022; Kauma and Swart, 2022).

Meanwhile, technology-driven interventions present new possibilities. Mobile advisory services—such as India's crop-specific hotlines and Rwanda's Smart Nkunganire System—have demonstrated the potential to enhance yields, input utilization, and resilience (Subramanian, 2021; Yenewa, 2023). Similar digital services in Tanzania and Senegal have improved access to fertilizers and market linkages (Ricome et al., 2024; Tende et al., 2021). However, uptake remains low in Malawi due to digital illiteracy and poor infrastructure (Mittal and Hariharan, 2018; Owusu et al., 2017; Steinke et al., 2019).

This study investigates the multifaceted and regionally differentiated dynamics of food insecurity in Malawi. It focuses on three interrelated objectives: (1) examining regional disparities and the socioeconomic, environmental, and market-related factors that influence food access; (2) analyzing the influence of cultural norms, inheritance practices, and gender on resource access; and (3) assessing farmers' awareness and willingness to adopt mobile advisory services. By bridging these dimensions, the study contributes to evidence-based, region-specific, and technology-enhanced strategies for reducing hunger and inequality in Malawi.

2. Design

2.1. Research design

In this study, both qualitative and quantitative data were collected

simultaneously, analyzed individually, and then combined to interpret the results. Employing qualitative research helped the researchers understand the daily lives, roadblocks, and systems affecting education in India that were hard to find through surveys alone.

The interviews enabled researchers to explore in greater detail how farmers perceive and respond to challenges such as climate change, inadequate service from extension staff, and a lack of information. Using different methods, the study confirmed and provided a better explanation of the differences in the regions. It was decided to use this design to gain a clear overview of food insecurity in regions by illustrating the patterns and the broader context behind them. It was particularly suitable given the need to triangulate survey-based trends with stakeholders' lived experiences across Malawi's diverse regions. By combining analysis of food shortages with the technological contributions of farmers, the research encompassed the full spectrum of food insecurity.

2.2. Population and sampling design

Researchers examined the circumstances of smallholder farmers in all regions of Malawi: the South, the Center, and the North. In the North, many farmers rely on rainfall, while in the middle region, their soil is depleting, and the South is vulnerable to natural disasters. Smallholder farmers and other stakeholders from these regions were engaged to capture various perspectives on food insecurity and technological interventions (ReliefWeb, 2024; UNICEF, 2023). For the quantitative part, the researchers chose stratified random sampling. Each of the three places was treated as a separate group. In every region, districts that reflected different types of environments, availability of roads and water, and their proximity to market areas were selected. Officers from the agricultural extension in the districts provided us with lists of smallholder farmers and randomly selected households by drawing from a computer-generated list. A total of 400 farmers (approximately 133 per region) were surveyed. The sample size was decided considering the population, its feasibility, and whether the stats would be comparable between regions.

The researcher employed purposive sampling to collect qualitative data, selecting 45 respondents, including smallholder farmers, community leaders, and agricultural officers. Researchers employed gender, age, and livelihood approaches, using food insecurity as a selection criterion. Community members were recruited with the help of the local extension system and village leaders. Sampling was conducted until various thematic information was obtained from people across regions and with various roles.

2.3. Data collection tools

The Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF) is a quantitative instrument to assess food security outcomes and farmers' engagement with mobile agricultural advisory services. The survey covered demographic characteristics, familiarity with mobile technologies, sources of agricultural information, and perceptions of mobile services. The instrument was reviewed by agricultural extension officers, digital technology specialists, and survey methodologists to ensure content validity and contextual relevance. A pilot test with 30 farmers from diverse regions evaluated item clarity, sequencing, and response variability. Based on this feedback, adjustments were made, and internal consistency across the constructs exceeded 0.80, as measured by Cronbach's alpha.

A semi-structured interview guide was developed using the SLF and key informant methodology for qualitative data collection. Interviews were conducted in local languages, translated, and back-translated to ensure accuracy. This approach enabled the study to explore lived experiences, food security challenges, and contextual factors that shape the adoption of mobile advisory services.

The study also featured a farmer-driven intervention, where farmers

actively engaged with prototype mobile advisory tools, including SMS and voice-based services, which provided weather forecasts, pest alerts, and market price updates. Structured feedback was collected through group discussions, enabling co-creation and ensuring the technology reflected farmers' realities. A follow-up survey was conducted to capture changes in perceptions and willingness to adopt after the intervention.

Food insecurity was measured using the Household Food Insecurity Access Scale (HFIAS) developed by USAID's Food and Nutrition Technical Assistance (FANTA) project. It records the difficulties the household encounters when accessing food within 30 days. There are nine standard measures in the HFIAS, which address increasing troubles related to food, ranging from uncertainty about whether there will be enough food to eating less per serving and even skipping a meal for a whole day.

Each respondent was asked if the illness had occurred in the last month and, if so, how often. 0 = Never, 1 = Rarely (1–2 times), 2 = Sometimes (3–10 times), and 3 = Often (>10 times). Each item's score was added up to calculate the HFIAS score, which ranges from 0 to 27, and the higher the score, the stronger the food insecurity. Similar to the FANTA approach, households were categorized into one of four levels of food insecurity. Those who enjoy a safe food supply, people who are mildly at risk of hunger, those who are moderately at risk, and those who have acute hunger and a lack of food.

The HFIAS was chosen because it is accurate in rural situations similar to those in Malawi and supports the main framework used, which combines stories and differences across the region. Since the scale was organized across several dimensions, researchers could compare results from different regions and determine how much land inequality contributed to or changed due to factors such as schooling, gender, property ownership, and the use of technology.

2.4. Data type and sources

The researchers utilized both primary and secondary data. Information was gathered using family surveys and semi-structured interviews. Secondary data sources included agricultural extension records, climate data, and market access statistics from the Malawi Ministry of Agriculture and the FAO.

2.5. Data analysis techniques

The quantitative data was analyzed using SPSS. We used basic statistics and table views to understand people's original positions and then paired t-tests and McNemar's tests helped us identify any differences before and after the campaign. The Kruskal-Wallis test revealed that people's education levels and regions significantly influence their outcomes. The regression model found that usefulness, ease of use of the products, and education were important factors in deciding whether someone would adopt the software. We included interaction terms to find any moderating effects and accessed the fit of our final models using AIC and Nagelkerke R^2 .

The conjoint analysis assessed farmers' preferences for service attributes (e.g., cost, delivery mode, timeliness), providing practical insights into designing user-centered services. The data was transcribed and then analyzed theme-wise in NVivo using the inductive coding method. It made it possible for rich subjects, such as meal insecurity, cultural obstacles, and regional divisions between nations, to emerge. Merging the two kinds of data allowed for triangulation, making the findings stronger and easier to understand.

2.6. Ethical clearance

This received ethical clearance from the National Committee on Research in the Social Sciences and Humanities under reference number NCST/RTT/2/6. All research protocols adhered to national ethical standards for the protection of human subjects.

Participation in this study was entirely voluntary. All participants were fully informed of the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and their rights prior to participation. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants. No personal data were released or shared without the explicit knowledge and permission of the individuals involved. Participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any stage without penalty. No vulnerable populations were included in this study. As required, evidence of ethical compliance is documented and available upon request.

3. Results

Analysis of the Household Food Insecurity Access Scale (HFIAS) scores revealed marked regional disparities in food insecurity levels. Households in the Southern region reported the highest food insecurity, with a mean score of 15.94 and a median of 16.00, indicating frequent experiences of anxiety over food access, meal reduction, and skipping meals. The Central region exhibited moderate food insecurity, with a mean of 12.50 and a median of 12.00. In contrast, the Northern region demonstrated the lowest severity, characterized by a mean score of 8.91 and a median of 9.00. The distribution of scores across regions reflects consistent trends observed in the qualitative data, with the Southern region disproportionately affected by structural vulnerability. Meanwhile, the North, although relatively food secure, remains constrained by market isolation and underutilized productive potential. [Table 1](#) shows the results.

[Table 2](#) illustrates a summary of blanket-based fertilizer application practices and average cultivable accessible land per capita in Malawi as reported by respondents

3.1. Crop type, vulnerability, and food insecurity

Food insecurity across Malawi is a multifaceted issue deeply interwoven with the agricultural practices and dominant crops cultivated in different regions. Each region's reliance on specific crops highlights unique vulnerabilities that exacerbate the broader challenge of ensuring sustainable food security. In the southern region, maize, rice, sorghum, millet, cassava, tea, and sugarcane are the primary crops, driving agricultural activity. However, this area faces recurrent environmental challenges, including cyclones and flash floods ([ReliefWeb. 2024; UNICEF, 2023](#)), which devastate crops and lead to persistent land fragmentation. The prioritization of cash crops, such as tea and sugarcane, for export further reduces the availability of arable land for subsistence farming, thereby exacerbating food insecurity. Dependency on relief aid following frequent natural disasters has fostered a culture of reliance, weakening local resilience and agricultural self-sufficiency. Political exploitation of food aid and disaster relief mechanisms further exacerbates the region's vulnerability, as short-term electoral strategies often overshadow long-term food security initiatives.

In the central region, the cultivation of maize, groundnuts, tobacco, and soybeans underscores its critical role in Malawi's agricultural economy. However, the region faces significant challenges related to soil degradation caused by continuous cultivation and over-reliance on generic inorganic fertilizers. This unsustainable practice has left soils infertile, resulting in declining crop yields. Compounding this issue are inadequate storage facilities and the high costs of insecticides, resulting in substantial post-harvest losses. Farmers' limited literacy levels hinder their understanding of soil health and sustainable farming practices, thereby entrenching their reliance on unsustainable inputs. Consequently, while the region contributes significantly to agricultural production, structural and systemic inefficiencies hinder its potential to ensure food security for its population. [Table 3](#) shows crops associated with each region and their respective challenges.

In the northern region, particularly in areas such as Karonga, rice, maize, millet, sorghum, cassava, and coffee are the primary crops. Although the region has significant irrigation potential, most agriculture

Table 1
Regional summary of Household Food Insecurity Access Scale (HFIAS) scores.

Region	N	Mean	Median	SD	Min	Max	25th %ile	75th %ile
Central	100	12.5	12	2.94	6	20	10	14.25
Northern	100	8.91	9	2.78	2	17	7	11
Southern	100	15.94	16	3.16	9	23	14	17.25

Note: HFIAS scores range from 0 to 27, with higher scores indicating greater severity of household food insecurity. The table presents descriptive statistics by region, including measures of central tendency, dispersion, and interquartile ranges. These results reflect differing regional experiences with food access challenges over the preceding 30 days, as captured through the standardized HFIAS instrument. Authors' survey data.

Table 2
Blanket-based fertilizer application practices and average cultivable accessible.

Region	Fertilizer Type	Application Rate (kg/ha)	Relative Average Plot Size (ha)	Fertilizer Applied per Plot (kg)*
Southern	UREA	100	0.5	50
Central	NPK	100	1.5	150
Northern	23:21:0	100	1.0	100

Note: Data supplied by smallholder farmers may not always be accurate due to self-reporting bias. Not all farmers can afford even subsidized fertilizers. Source: Authors' survey data.

remains rain-fed, making it highly vulnerable to climate variability (Trócaire, n.d.). Limited access to markets and mechanized farming technologies constrains productivity and income generation, preventing farmers from investing in sustainable agricultural improvements. The underutilization of available resources and lack of diversification in farming practices diminish resilience to climatic shocks and market fluctuations.

These interconnected factors demonstrate the complexity of food insecurity across Malawi. Environmental challenges, such as floods and land degradation (Government of Malawi, 2023a), are compounded by the reliance on monoculture cash crops (Government of Malawi, 2023b) and unsustainable agricultural inputs. Socioeconomic constraints, including low literacy levels and limited access to technology and markets, further exacerbate these challenges. The interplay between these factors leads to cyclical poverty and persistent hunger, underscoring the need for region-specific interventions that address both systemic and localized challenges. Effective strategies must strike a balance between short-term relief and long-term solutions, such as sustainable land management, diversified cropping systems, improved storage facilities, and enhanced access to education and agricultural technologies. Without such an integrated approach, persistent vulnerabilities across regions will continue undermining food security in Malawi.

A thematic analysis led to the development of several codes and corresponding themes, which yielded a more refined final list of themes. Table 4 summarizes codes and theme development.

The word cloud in Fig. 1 indicates that food insecurity in Malawi results from multiple social, political, economic, environmental, and geographical challenges (Fig. 2).

Table 3
Regional crops and their related food security challenges.

Region	Dominant Crops	Food Security Challenges
South	Maize, rice, sorghum, millet, cassava, tea, sugarcane	Frequent cyclones, flash floods, land fragmentation, reliance on cash crops, lack of arable land, dependency culture, and political exploitation.
Central	Maize, groundnuts, tobacco, soybeans	Soil degradation, over-reliance on inorganic fertilizers, inadequate storage facilities, low literacy rates, and a lack of knowledge about sustainable farming practices.
North (Karonga)	Rice, maize, millet, sorghum, cassava, coffee	Vulnerability to climate change, underutilized irrigation potential, limited market access, dependency on rain-fed agriculture, and lack of mechanization.

3.2. Socio-cultural factors

The study revealed that traditions, including marriage systems, gender inequalities, and resistance to change, play a significant role in shaping food insecurity across Malawi. In the southern region, the matrilineal inheritance system, where land and property pass through the female line, has contributed to weak family structures and disrupted intergenerational knowledge transfer. Men, lacking authority over land and domestic plans, often move away to follow their wives, leaving mothers as single household heads. However, these mothers traditionally are not responsible for training children in farming or other survival skills, which are customarily assigned to uncles. This arrangement frequently results in children being left without adequate guidance, contributing to high illiteracy rates and a generation of youth unequipped to participate meaningfully in agriculture or the broader economy.

"In our culture, the land belongs to women, but that doesn't mean they have the skills to manage it properly. Men have no say, and uncles who should help are often nowhere to be found." (S001CM)

"Young people here don't know how to farm because no one teaches them. Mothers are busy surviving, and the men are off elsewhere. It's the children who suffer in the end." (S003CM)

"Traditional systems in the South are disintegrating, leaving women with too much responsibility and too little support. These dynamics create a vicious cycle of dependency and poor agricultural outcomes." (A/S001)

In the northern and central regions, deeply entrenched gender roles further exacerbate food insecurity. Women often have limited decision-making power and restricted access to resources, marginalizing them in agricultural and household decision-making processes. Resistance to modern agricultural practices further hampers productivity.

"Men control everything in this community—land, finances, and decisions about what to plant—but when things go wrong, they blame the women." (N002CM)

"We stick to what our fathers did. Even when the yields are poor, many of us are reluctant to try new ways of farming because it's risky." (C001CM)

"Cultural norms in Malawi are deeply rooted, making it difficult to introduce innovations that challenge long-standing practices." (A/S002)

Across all regions, traditional practices and resistance to modern

Table 4
Coding summary.

Respondent Code	Quotations	Themes	Refined Themes
Q1 C001	“We face prolonged dry spells that destroy our crops.”	Climate challenges	Environmental constraints
	“The cost of fertilizers has skyrocketed, making it difficult for us to improve yields.”	Resource limitations	
	“Most of our farming tools are outdated and inefficient.”	Lack of modern tools	
C002	“Seasonal rains are becoming unpredictable, and this affects planting schedules.”	Climate variability	
	“Flooding during the rainy season destroys not just crops but homes as well.”	Natural disasters	
	“Government subsidies are inadequate and don’t reach most of us.”	Lack of government support	
Q2 C003	“Transportation to markets costs more than we earn from selling our produce.”	Market access issues	Structural barriers to food access
	“We lose many harvests due to poor storage facilities, especially for maize.”	Post-harvest losses	
C004	“Middlemen exploit us because we don’t have direct market access.”	Exploitation in market systems	
	“The few cooperatives we have can’t compete with private buyers.”	Weak cooperative systems	
Q3 C005	“Men dominate decision-making in farming, which sidelines women in major agricultural activities.”	Gender roles and cultural norms	Social and cultural barriers
	“Women are expected to focus on household tasks rather than participate in large-scale farming.”	Gendered division of labor	
C006	“Cultural norms discourage women from inheriting land, limiting their farming potential.”	Land inheritance inequality	
Q4 C007	“We rely heavily on money sent from family members working in nearby towns.”	Financial reliance on remittances	Economic coping mechanisms
	“Without remittances, we can’t afford even the most necessities.”	Income insecurity	
C008	“Community groups often help during food shortages, but the assistance is temporary.”	Community-based social support	
	“NGOs provide seeds and fertilizers, but these are one-time donations and unsustainable.”	External interventions	

agricultural methods prevent farmers from adopting sustainable and innovative approaches. For instance, many farmers are reluctant to diversify crops or experiment with advanced farming techniques, preferring to adhere to familiar, albeit less productive, practices. These socio-cultural dynamics underscore how deeply ingrained traditions and

gender inequities impede progress toward achieving food security in Malawi.

3.3. Environmental and climate-driven challenges

Environmental and climate-related challenges emerged as critical factors contributing to food insecurity, with distinct regional variations. In the southern region, frequent cyclones and flash floods, often originating from the Mozambican coastline, cause annual devastation to crops, livestock, and infrastructure. Many farmers, particularly those in vulnerable, low-lying valleys, refuse to relocate to safer upland areas due to their cultural attachment to ancestral lands, thereby exacerbating their vulnerability. The unpredictability and intensity of these natural disasters leave some farmers unwilling to cultivate, fearing they will lose their efforts to impending disasters.

“Every year, the floods take everything we’ve planted, but we can’t just leave the land of our ancestors. Where would we even go?” (S005CM)

“I have stopped planting along the valley because the water keeps destroying everything. But my neighbor still plants there, hoping the floods won’t come again.” (S004CM)

“Southern Malawi is a textbook example of how climate change interacts with cultural attachment to land, creating a cycle of vulnerability.” (A/S003)

In the central and northern regions, continuous cultivation without allowing the land to regenerate has led to severe soil leaching and degradation. This issue is compounded by an over-reliance on generic inorganic fertilizers, which are applied uniformly without consideration for the specific chemical and physical properties of local soils. As a result, soil health has deteriorated, leading to declining yields and increased dependency on external inputs. These environmental challenges are further exacerbated by a lack of adaptation strategies to cope with the changing climate, leaving farmers ill-prepared to address the impacts of irregular rainfall patterns, droughts, and floods.

“We’ve been farming the same plots for years, and now the soil is so tired it hardly produces anything, even with fertilizers.” (N004CM)

“No one tells us how to use the fertilizers properly. We just apply them the way we were shown years ago, but it’s not working anymore.” (C003CM)

“The impact of soil degradation in Malawi is a silent crisis. It’s not just an environmental issue but a major driver of food insecurity.” (A/S004)

3.4. Economic and market barriers

Economic constraints and market barriers significantly affect food security across all regions. Land fragmentation is a pervasive issue in the southern region, with large-scale commercial estates dedicated to cash crops like tea occupying the most fertile lands. This leaves smallholder farmers with inadequate plots for subsistence farming, further limiting their ability to achieve food sufficiency.

“The tea estates take all the good land, and we’re left with rocky patches where even maize struggles to grow.” (S006CM)

“I tried to expand my land, but it’s so fragmented I can’t even grow enough to feed my family, let alone sell anything.” (S002CM)

“The economic marginalization of smallholder farmers in the south is directly tied to land access and market inequities.” (A/S005)

Additionally, poor market systems create opportunities for intermediaries to exploit farmers, forcing them to sell their produce at low prices only to repurchase it later at inflated rates. This cycle of

“Without proper storage and pest control measures, even a good harvest ends up wasted. This discourages many farmers from investing in improved seeds or fertilizers for the next season.” (C006CM)

These challenges are compounded by limited financial capacity, as expressed by one respondent:

“Buying fertilizer is already difficult for us. Adding the cost of insecticides and storage solutions is just impossible.” (C004CM)

Academicians highlight the structural barriers contributing to these economic difficulties:

“Farmers in these regions face a vicious cycle of low yields, inadequate storage, and poor market access, which perpetuates poverty and food insecurity.” (A/S002)

“The lack of investment in rural infrastructure, particularly storage facilities, makes it almost inevitable that farmers will suffer post-harvest losses year after year.” (A/S005)

These interlinked issues underscore the urgent need for integrated interventions that target storage infrastructure, pest management, and input affordability to break the cycle of low productivity and persistent food insecurity.

3.5. Political and governance-related challenges

The study identified governance issues and political dynamics as significant contributors to food insecurity. In the southern region, repeated natural disasters and subsequent relief provisions from government and non-governmental organizations have fostered a culture of dependency. Some farmers avoid cultivating their fields, anticipating that relief aid will arrive after disasters. Opposition politicians exploit delays or inadequacies in aid distribution as a campaign strategy, deepening tribal and regional political divides.

“We know the government will bring food aid after the floods, so many people don’t see the point of farming anymore.” (S007CM)

“Politicians use food aid to win support. If it comes late, they blame the other party. It’s always a political game.” (S008CM)

“The politicization of food insecurity undermines genuine efforts to create sustainable solutions. It’s a governance failure at every level.” (A/S007)

In the central and northern regions, the mismanagement of fertilizer subsidies has left many farmers reliant on generic inorganic fertilizers, which often fail to address the specific needs of their soils. Although some may not access such subsidies, the policy perpetuates misconceptions that harvesting will rely solely on fertilizers. Those who cannot access such fertilizers often fail to practice relevant crop husbandry practices, such as timely weeding, since they have already given up on these farms without inorganic fertilizers.

“We depend on these fertilizers, but the prices keep going up, and sometimes the subsidies don’t even reach us.” (N006CM)

“The government promises support, but what we get is either too late or not enough to make a real difference.” (C005CM)

“The mismanagement of agricultural subsidies highlights systemic flaws in Malawi’s governance structure.” (A/S008).

Weak enforcement of agricultural policies across all regions has further hindered efforts to address food insecurity. For instance, policies designed to regulate grain pricing and storage are often poorly implemented, allowing intermediaries and business moguls to exploit farmers.

The government tells us there are set prices for grain, but when we sell, the middlemen dictate their prices, and we have no choice but to accept.” (C002CM)

“Every year, they announce policies to help us, but in reality, no one enforces them. The rich buyers get away with exploiting small farmers like us.” (N004CM)

“We hear about these laws to protect us from unfair practices, but I have never seen them work in our favor. The markets are controlled by people who care only about profits.” (S005CM)

These governance-related challenges reveal systemic weaknesses in resource management and policy enforcement, exacerbating food insecurity nationwide.

“Without proper monitoring and implementation, policies are just words. Farmers are left at the mercy of market forces and powerful traders.” (A/S004)

“The policy frameworks exist, but the lack of accountability means that they rarely translate into real benefits for the farmers.” (A/S006)

“We need strong systems to regulate grain markets, but corruption and political interference undermine every effort to create fair practices.” (C003CM)

3.6. Knowledge and capacity gaps

Knowledge and capacity gaps are critical barriers to food security in Malawi. Low literacy levels limit farmers’ understanding of sustainable agricultural practices and soil-specific farming techniques. Fueled by a lack of awareness and technical support, reluctance to adopt modern technologies further perpetuates unsustainable practices.

“I’ve heard about irrigation systems, but they’re too expensive, and no one teaches us how to use them.” (S009CM)

“Even if we want to change, we don’t have the resources or the knowledge to make it happen.” (C007CM)

The gap between knowledge and practice in Malawi’s agricultural sector presents a significant challenge that requires immediate attention.

Across all regions, there is a general reluctance to adopt modern agricultural technologies and sustainable practices due to a lack of technical knowledge and access to training. Traditional beliefs and skepticism about new methods further inhibit progress. For instance, farmers continue to rely on outdated techniques despite evidence of their declining productivity. This resistance to change highlights the urgent need for targeted educational and training programs to equip farmers with the knowledge and skills necessary to enhance agricultural practices and achieve food security.

“Most of us don’t know much about soil health. We just farm the way we were taught by our parents, even if the yields are getting worse.” (C006CM)

“When they talk about modern farming, it sounds good, but no one shows us how to do it properly.” (N007CM)

“Education and training are the missing links in Malawi’s fight against food insecurity. Without them, progress will remain elusive.” (A/S009)

These findings reveal the complex interplay of socio-cultural, environmental, economic, political, and knowledge-related factors contributing to food insecurity in Malawi. While each region faces unique challenges, overarching issues such as soil degradation, inadequate storage infrastructure, and poor policy enforcement affect all regions. Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive approach

considering regional variations while implementing systemic reforms to promote sustainable agricultural practices, enhance market access, and improve governance and resource management.

3.7. Farmer-driven insights

Table 5 summarizes the results of a Kruskal-Wallis H test assessing differences in two variables, Willingness to Adopt and Perceived Usefulness, across four education levels: No Education, Primary, Secondary, and College. Median scores with interquartile ranges are presented for each education group. For both variables, median scores increase progressively with higher education levels, reflecting greater willingness and perceived usefulness among participants with more education.

The Kruskal-Wallis H test results show statistically significant differences across the groups for both variables, with $H(3) = 22.15$ for Willingness to Adopt and $H(3) = 18.72$ for Perceived Usefulness, both with p -values less than 0.001. Post-hoc analyses reveal that individuals with no education have significantly lower scores than all other groups, while no significant difference is observed between the Secondary and College groups, which exhibit similar levels of willingness and perceived usefulness. This highlights the positive relationship between education level and openness to adopting mobile advisory services and their perceived value.

3.7.1. Willingness to adopt mobile advisory services and perceived usefulness

The analysis highlights that education level significantly influences willingness to adopt mobile advisory services and perceived usefulness. Farmers with no education reported the lowest willingness to adopt (Median = 3.0, IQR = 2.5–3.5), while those with college-level education demonstrated the highest willingness (Median = 5.0, IQR = 4.5–5.0). The Kruskal-Wallis test confirmed statistically significant differences across education levels ($H(3) = 22.15$, $p < 0.001$), with post-hoc comparisons showing that the no-education group scored significantly lower than all other groups, though secondary and college groups did not differ significantly. A similar trend emerged for perceived usefulness, with farmers having no education reporting a lower perception of utility (Median = 3.5, IQR = 3.0–4.0) compared to those with higher education levels (Median = 5.0, IQR = 4.5–5.0). The Kruskal-Wallis analysis for perceived usefulness ($H(3) = 18.72$, $p < 0.001$) also indicated significant differences, particularly between lower and higher education groups (See Table 6).

These findings emphasize that education is critical in shaping perceptions and willingness to adopt. Farmers with higher education levels exhibit greater enthusiasm and acknowledgment of the benefits of mobile advisory services. This suggests a need for targeted interventions to address the lower willingness to adopt and perceived usefulness among less-educated farmers. Tailored training and awareness campaigns, particularly for individuals with limited literacy, can help bridge the gap and ensure equitable access and utility across all educational levels.

We regressed farmers' willingness to adopt mobile advisory services on key predictors, including perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and education level. The results of the logistic regression indicate that perceived usefulness significantly predicts adoption, with an odds ratio (OR) of 2.3 (SE = 0.15, 95 % CI [1.9, 2.7], $p = .001$). This suggests that a unit increase in perceived usefulness more than doubles the odds of adoption. Perceived ease of use also emerged as a significant predictor, with an OR of 1.8 (SE = 0.18, 95 % CI [1.5, 2.2], $p = .002$), highlighting the necessity of user-friendly service designs. Education level

significantly influenced adoption likelihood, with an OR of 1.5 (SE = 0.12, 95 % CI [1.2, 1.8], $p = .015$), suggesting higher education levels enhance openness to these technologies.

We conducted a conjoint analysis to determine the relative importance of key service attributes that influence farmers' preferences. Table 7 presents the regression and conjoint analysis results, indicating the predictors of farmers' willingness to adopt mobile advisory services and their preferences for service attributes.

Cost was the most influential factor, contributing 45.3 % of the total importance (SE = 0.21, 95 % CI [40.8, 49.8]), followed by the mode of delivery, which accounted for 32.7 % (SE = 0.18, 95 % CI [28.5, 36.8]). Timeliness contributed 22.0 % (SE = 0.20, 95 % CI [18.2, 25.8]), reflecting the critical role of timely advisory services in decision-making.

Building on this foundation, interaction effects were explored to determine how contextual factors, such as education level and access to resources, moderate these relationships. Together, these analyses provide a comprehensive understanding, combining practical drivers of adoption with behavioral and contextual insights.

Willingness to Adopt Mobile Advisory Services by Region

A Kruskal-Wallis H test examined differences in willingness to adopt mobile advisory services across Malawi's three regions (N = 400). The test revealed a statistically significant difference, $H(2) = 66.82$, $p < 0.001$, with a small-to-moderate effect size ($\eta^2 = 0.17$). Median willingness scores were lowest in the Southern region (Median = 3.3, IQR = 2.9–3.8), moderate in the Central region (Median = 4.1, IQR = 3.6–4.5), and highest in the Northern region (Median = 4.4, IQR = 4.1–4.8), demonstrating the regional differences.

The figure displays a combined violin plot, strip plot, and box plot showing the distribution of farmers' willingness to adopt mobile advisory services across Malawi's Southern, Central, and Northern regions. The boxplots represent the median and interquartile ranges (IQR), while the violin contours indicate response density. Individual responses are plotted as jittered points.

3.7.2. Interaction effects results

The interaction effects analysis revealed that education level significantly moderates the relationship between perceived usefulness and adoption likelihood (OR = 2.05, 95 % CI [1.72, 2.38], $p < .001$). Farmers with higher education levels exhibited a stronger positive association between perceived usefulness and adoption. Similarly, digital literacy moderated the effect of perceived ease of use on adoption ($B = 0.27$, SE = 0.05, $p < .01$), indicating that farmers with greater digital literacy were likelier to adopt services they found easy to use.

Logistic regression with interaction terms showed robust model fit statistics. This logistic regression model includes perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and education level as predictors, offering an adjusted analysis of factors influencing willingness to adopt. The interaction model adds cross-product terms between perceived usefulness and education level, as well as ease of use and digital literacy, providing insight into potential moderating effects. These models contrast the earlier unadjusted Kruskal-Wallis comparisons included for preliminary group-level exploration. The regression, with a Nagelkerke R^2 of 0.46 and a Hosmer-Lemeshow p -value of 0.68, suggests a good fit. The inclusion of interaction terms improved predictive power, as indicated by a reduction in the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) from 115.4 (primary effects model) to 108.6 (interaction model). These findings highlight that contextual factors, such as education and digital literacy, significantly influence how farmers perceive and respond to mobile

Table 5
Kruskal-Wallis H test assessing Willingness to Adopt and Perceived Usefulness across four education levels.

Variable	No Education	Primary	Secondary	College	Kruskal-Wallis H	p-value	Post-Hoc Notes
Willingness to Adopt	3.0 (2.5–3.5)	4.0 (3.5–4.5)	4.5 (4.0–5.0)	5.0 (4.5–5.0)	$H(3) = 22.15$	< 0.001	No Education < all, Secondary = College
Perceived Usefulness	3.5 (3.0–4.0)	4.0 (3.5–4.5)	4.5 (4.0–5.0)	5.0 (4.5–5.0)	$H(3) = 18.72$	< 0.001	Similar trends above

Table 6
Willingness to adopt mobile advisory services and perceived usefulness.

Variable	No Education	Primary	Secondary	College	$\chi^2 / F / H$	p-value	Post-Hoc Notes
Awareness Pre (%)	15	30	50	75	$\chi^2(3) = 25.87$	<0.001	Significant increase in all groups
Awareness Post (%)	65	80	85	90			
Willingness to Adopt	Median =3.0	Median =4.0	Median =4.5	Median =5.0	H(3) =22.15	<0.001	No education lower than others
Perceived Usefulness (M)	3.8 (0.9)	4.2 (0.8)	4.6 (0.6)	4.8 (0.5)	F(3, 396) =18.45	<0.001	All groups differ significantly

Table 7
Key findings from logistic regression and conjoint analysis.

Variable	Statistical Test	Odds Ratio/Importance %	SE	95 % CI	p-value	VIF	Model Fit
Perceived Usefulness	Logistic Regression	2.3	0.15	[1.9–2.7]	0.001	1.6	Nagelkerke $R^2 = 0.42$; AIC = 112.3
Perceived Ease of Use	Logistic Regression	1.8	0.18	[1.5–2.2]	0.002	1.8	VIF < 2.0
Education Level	Logistic Regression	1.5	0.12	[1.2–1.8]	0.015	1.5	Hosmer-Lemeshow $p = 0.62$
Cost of Service	Conjoint Analysis	45.3	0.21	[40.8–49.8]	-	1.7	$R^2 = 0.68$
Mode of Delivery	Conjoint Analysis	32.7	0.18	[28.5–36.8]	-	1.6	Preference Level CI = [28.5–36.8]
Timeliness	Conjoint Analysis	22.0	0.20	[18.2–25.8]	-	1.5	Pseudo $R^2 = 0.56$

advisory services, underscoring the need for tailored interventions to maximize adoption across diverse farmer groups.

4. Discussion

4.1. Regional systems of vulnerability: intersections of environment, markets, and sociocultural norms

4.1.1. Southern region

Food insecurity in Malawi's southern region stems from environmental stress, traditional cultural landholding practices, and the country's reliance on external aid. The region's matrilineal inheritance system, while securing land access for women, paradoxically limits male investment in agriculture, weakening long-term productivity. As a result, families' ability to sustain themselves diminishes due to interruptions in passing down farming knowledge, working the land, and planning.

The repeated need for humanitarian aid further complicates the situation, often resulting from floods and other natural disasters. These conditions reinforce short-term coping strategies and dependency patterns, aligning with Kauma and Swart's (2022) critique of aid politicization and Komushaago et al. (2023) assessment of fragmented landholdings. Furthermore, widespread blanket fertilizer practices exacerbate soil acidification (Yang et al., 2018), diminishing nutrient availability and reinforcing unsustainable practices (Chilumpha et al., 2024). The combination of environmental degradation, ineffective input use, and fragmented governance structures illustrates a multidimensional failure across the capitals of the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework—natural, human, social, and institutional.

This suggests that policy should help countries transition from routine aid that depends on politics to ensuring that different groups participate in local-level planning for soil management, land division, and finding local ways to cope with floods.

4.1.2. Central region

Food insecurity is prevalent in the Central region due to soil degradation, market disruptions, and a lack of agricultural knowledge. While the agroecological potential is relatively favorable, continuous cultivation without organic replenishment has depleted soil organic matter, corroborating the observations of Zuza et al. (2023). Relying on fertilizers without assessing soil quality over time has led to declining yields and unbalanced nutrient levels.

A lack of education and an inability to read make it easier for people to engage in unsustainable practices. On this basis, it can be argued that the lack of technical knowledge, rather than resource shortages, hinders the human ability to adapt; therefore, training must focus on skills rather

than merely providing the necessary resources. Poor storage infrastructure and exploitative intermediary systems (Kauma & Swart, 2022) further trap farmers in cycles of post-harvest losses and depressed prices. Various farmer courses, local soil assessments, and increased investment in storage are essential in helping this area overcome the problem.

4.1.3. Northern region

In comparison, northern Malawi does not face as many land disputes, but it uses irrigation less effectively and is isolated from the main markets. Because the property can be passed down from father to son, it has kept men more involved in farming. However, the region remains institutionally peripheral, receiving limited investment and support (Chinsinga, 2005). Despite its favorable land and water resources, farmers in Malawi rely almost entirely on rain-fed agriculture (Trócaire, n.d.), and blanket fertilizer recommendations often fail to capitalize on the unique regional soil characteristics (Beg et al., 2024; Aliyu et al., 2023).

Higher education and reduced dependency on aid may enable citizens to become more digitally engaged in their lives. At the same time, markets that are not open to trade limit the money that can be earned and the resources a business can use. Since the government often neglects remote areas, the region cannot help reduce the problem of national food shortages.

To address these challenges, we should enhance local water usage, improve rural transportation, and fully utilize digital advisory programs in collaboration with local groups.

4.2. Cross-cutting drivers: fertilizer policy, gender norms, and governance failures

4.2.1. Blanket fertilizer practices and agronomic efficacy

As this study confirms, the widespread application of uniform fertilizer formulations (e.g., UREA, NPK) across Malawi contradicts agronomic best practices, which require adaptation to local soil chemistry (Chilumpha et al., 2024; Titirmare et al., 2023). When the economy is not in sync with the environment, the results hurt nature to a large extent. Phosphorus fixation, leaching, and mineral uptake imbalances, especially in already degraded or acidic soils (Dhull et al., 2004). As a result, Malawi's extension and fertilizer subsidy programs fail to account for the highly diverse needs of local farmers.

4.3. Socio-cultural dynamics and gendered inequities

The analysis enables us to understand better how gender-based land rules and customs influence participation in farming. In the South, matrilineal systems have contributed to intergenerational literacy gaps

and diminished male involvement in farming, while in the North, patrilineal norms restrict women's access to decision-making and assets (UN Women, UNDP, & UNEP, n.d.). Therefore, it is evident that policies should be designed with local cultures in mind, providing everyone with equal opportunities without compromising local customs.

Moreover, reluctance to adopt new practices is not due to resistance to change but rather to rational assessments of risk under economic precarity—a finding consistent with Najam et al. (2023). As a result, future programs should offer new ideas, secure financial systems, and training to reduce the chance of adoption not working out.

4.4. Market constraints and economic cycles

This study substantiates earlier findings on market barriers (Azomahou et al., 2022), demonstrating how a lack of storage facilities and monopolistic intermediaries creates a post-harvest loss and price exploitation cycle. The inability to store grain forces premature sales at low prices, followed by repurchases at higher costs—an unsustainable pattern noted across all regions.

Policy responses must include investment in rural storage and regulated input/output pricing to reduce dependency on informal markets.

4.5. Governance failures and policy gaps

Echoing Banik and Chasukwa (2019), this study demonstrates that agricultural governance in Malawi is marked by politicization, short-termism, and weak enforcement. Disaster relief in the South is often synchronized with electoral cycles, while fertilizer subsidy mismanagement in the Central and Northern regions contributes to misinformation and misuse. This erodes trust in government and disrupts productive planning cycles.

Institutional reforms must focus on transparency, de-politicizing aid and input programs, and evidence-based agricultural budgeting.

4.6. Knowledge, capacity, and technology adoption

Capacity gaps are most evident in the relationship between education and openness to innovation. As the analysis of mobile advisory service adoption reveals, farmers with higher education levels are significantly more likely to perceive usefulness and ease of use, aligning with Oli et al. (2025) diffusion theory. Perceived usefulness (OR = 2.3) and ease of use (OR = 1.8) were the strongest predictors of adoption, while cost emerged as the most crucial attribute in conjoint analysis (45.3 %).

Interaction effects underscore that technological design must consider user profiles: farmers with higher digital literacy respond more positively to ease-of-use improvements. These insights justify stratified training programs and suggest that mobile advisory platforms must be affordable and cognitively accessible to be effective.

4.7. Toward integrated, region-specific solutions

Collectively, these findings call for a paradigm shift from uniform agricultural policies to regionally differentiated and culturally grounded interventions. Acknowledging the heterogeneous realities of Malawi's farming communities—regarding land tenure, market access, soil conditions, or social norms—is foundational to building resilient, equitable food systems. Policy must transition from reactive, input-centric models to integrated, forward-looking strategies prioritizing institutional accountability, farmer agency, and spatial equity.

5. Conclusion and implications

This study examines the food insecurity faced by different regions in Malawi, providing practical examples to help us understand the leading

causes of the problem. Examining factors such as the environment, the market, people's cultures, and the technology they use reveals that food insecurity does not appear everywhere; it varies depending on factors like where people live and their respective communities.

First, adhering to the same blanket fertilizer rules, regardless of the land's location, demonstrates the importance of switching to fertilizers that match the specific soil types in each region, utilizing testing and information from local experts. Second, the way land ownership is often passed down by gender, whether to women or men, suggests that changing land rules at a local level is necessary to ensure both women and young people have fair access to land they can use to grow food, without disregarding traditions. Third, because things like grain markets and how crops are stored do not always match up well with actual harvests, especially in parts of the Central and Northern regions, putting money into better ways to store crops and help keep prices steady can help prevent a lot of grain being wasted and farmers getting taken advantage of after the harvest.

The differential willingness to adopt mobile advisory services also suggests that it is essential to create farm technologies that are affordable and easy to use, aligning with people's knowledge and ability with technology. This means we need digital extension tools that incorporate feedback from farmers and support individuals with diverse perspectives and varying levels of access to technology.

The study makes the following recommendations:

Develop and implement a countrywide soil fertility plan, ensuring it is tailored to local needs and conditions in each region.

Reorient agricultural extension and education to focus more on working with communities, ensuring they fit local customs, and helping address any differences people might have in knowledge.

Institutionalize infrastructure development plans to support farming, such as storage, irrigation, and improved roads, especially in areas where growers use large amounts of water and require assistance, like in the country's north.

The pilot rolled out programs that combined the use of helpful computer tools and safety-net services and involved people in designing the solution.

Table 8 presents the Region-Specific Policy Recommendation Matrix, which links regional challenges with targeted interventions and identifies responsible policy actors.

Given how complex food insecurity is, future research should look into things like why some places have more problems with food insecurity than others, how things like climate and government help or hinder people's access to food, and what can be done to help people who are struggling to get enough to eat.

Investigate the way governments and other local groups decide to give out subsidies and how aid money is used, especially if it makes inequality worse between different parts of the country.

Conduct longitudinal, region-specific impact assessments of

Table 8
Regional Differences in Willingness to Adopt Mobile Advisory Services in Malawi.

Region	Median Willingness Score	Interquartile Range (IQR)
Southern	3.3	2.9–3.8
Central	4.1	3.6–4.5
Northern	4.4	4.1–4.8
Test Statistic (H)	66.82	
p-value	< 0.001	
Effect Size (η^2)	0.17	
Sample Size (N)	400	

Note: This table presents the median willingness scores and interquartile ranges (IQR) for adopting mobile agricultural advisory services across Malawi's Southern, Central, and Northern regions. The Kruskal-Wallis H test results indicate a statistically significant difference among the regions.

Fig. 1 indicates that food insecurity in Malawi results from multiple social, political, economic, environmental, and geographical challenges

decentralized policy interventions (e.g., land governance, market regulation, climate adaptation).

Explore how digital services impact people's ability to make choices, particularly for those often excluded, so we can develop more inclusive approaches to generating new ideas.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jane Thokozani Banda: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **George N. Chidimbah Munthali:** Resources, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Chigonjetso Victoria Banda:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration. **Lazarus Obed Livingstone Banda:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declarations

This study did not receive funding from any individual or organization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.foohum.2025.100695](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foohum.2025.100695).

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